

Counter-framing nonviolent coercion: The case of the *escraches* by the PAH in the press

El contraenmarcado de la coercion no violenta: El caso de los escraches de la PAH en la prensa

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Abstract

This paper explores the efficacy of counter-framing processes vis-à-vis non-violence meanings constructed by protest movements. We empirically analyse the case of the successful counter-framing that the Mortgages Victims' Platform (PAH) suffered in Spain in 2013 as a response to its campaign of personalized *escraches* against some notorious governmental opponents. Our case study suggests that meanings associated to so-called "nonviolent coercion" tactics, such as *escraches*, are highly vulnerable to counter-framing.

The most instrumentalist currents within non-violence studies, following the seminal work of Sharp (1973), have intended to accommodate "nonviolent coercion" as a legitimate and efficacious means of protest. Such stance is built on a minimalist notion of non-violence, which does not exclude psychological coercion and its personalization. However, insofar as, according to such currents, non-violence meanings contribute to the success of protest mainly through the conversion of public opinion, the relevant notion of non-violence is not the one prevailing into the academic and activist literatures, but the one predominating in a given political culture.

There are good reasons to believe that the Spanish public opinion has consistently maintained rather strict attitudes of non-violence across the ideological and partisan spectrum since the transition to democracy in the late 1970s, in accordance with the long-lasting hegemonic narratives concerning recent history and Basque terrorism. This, in principle, facilitated the efficacy of the non-violence meanings articulated by protestors. Altogether, it is in the key conflictive protest episodes, such as *escraches*, when the credibility of such meanings is really at stake in the public sphere.

Our specific object of analysis is the counter-framing surrounding the *escrache* to the member of parliament (MP) and deputy secretary of the ruling People's party (PP) Esteban González Pons (03/20/2013). Through content analysis of a selection of pieces of information extracted from the most important Spanish newspaper, *El País*, we shall examine the extent to which counter-framing successfully challenged one of the main dimensions that, according to the literature, confers credibility to frames and packages of meanings tied to frames: consistency, understood as congruency between constructed meanings and tactical actions.

Keywords

Counter-framing; non-violence; protest movements; Spain; PAH.

Resumen

Este trabajo explora la eficacia de los procesos de contraenmarcado atinentes a los significados de no violencia contruidos por los movimientos de protesta. Analizamos empíricamente el caso del exitoso contraenmarcado que la Plataforma de Afectados por la Hipoteca (PAH) sufrió en España en 2013, como respuesta a su campaña de escraches personalizados contra algunos notorios oponentes

gubernamentales. Nuestro estudio de caso sugiere que los significados asociados a las denominadas tácticas de “coerción no violenta”, como los escraches, son muy vulnerables al contraenmarcado.

Las corrientes más instrumentalistas dentro de los estudios de no violencia, siguiendo el trabajo seminal de Sharp (1973), han tratado de acomodar la “coerción no violenta” como un medio legítimo y eficaz de protesta. Tal postura está construida sobre una noción minimalista de no violencia, que no excluye la coerción psicológica y su personalización. Sin embargo, en la medida en que, según tales corrientes, los significados de no violencia contribuyen al éxito de la protesta principalmente a través de la conversión de la opinión pública, la noción relevante de no violencia no es la prevalente en las literaturas académica y activista, sino la predominante en una determinada cultura política.

Hay buenas razones para creer que la opinión pública española ha mantenido actitudes más bien estrictas de no violencia a través del espectro ideológico y partidista desde la transición a la democracia a finales de 1970, en concordancia con las longevas narrativas hegemónicas referentes a la historia reciente y el terrorismo vasco. Esto, en principio, facilitaba la eficacia de los significados de no violencia articulados por los movimientos de protesta. Pero es en los episodios conflictivos clave de protesta, como los escraches, cuando la credibilidad de dichos significados se pone realmente en juego en la esfera pública.

Nuestro objeto específico de análisis es el contraenmarcado en torno al escrache al diputado y vicesecretario del gubernamental Partido Popular Esteban González Pons (20/03/2013). A través del análisis de contenido de una selección de piezas de información extraídas del diario español más relevante, El País, examinaremos la medida en que dicho contraenmarcado tuvo éxito a la hora de comprometer una de las principales dimensiones que, según la literatura, confiere credibilidad a los marcos y paquetes de significados vinculados a los marcos: la consistencia, entendida como congruencia entre significados contruidos y acciones tácticas.

Palabras clave

Contraenmarcado; no violencia; movimientos de protesta; España; PAH.

Introduction

The aim of this paper is to emphasise the problematic communicative nature of “nonviolent coercion” tactics eventually employed by protest movements. In opposition to authors such as Samad (2008), who, following the seminal work of Sharp (1973), have attempted to conceptually accommodate “coercive nonviolence” tactics as a valid and efficacious catalogue of nonviolent actions, we tend to believe that the meanings associated to such catalogue are highly vulnerable to potential counter-framing. When counter-framing occurs, the communicative efficacy and, ultimately, the credibility of a given social movement organization (SMO) is highly at stake, especially when it has publicly been committed to non-violence. We shall support our stance with the case study of the successful counter-framing that the Mortgages Victims’ Platform (PAH)

suffered in Spain in 2013, as a response to its campaign of personalized *escraches* against some notorious governmental opponents.

1. Nonviolent coercion and public opinion: the Spanish case

Non-violence meanings hold a prominent place into the repertoire of symbolic artifacts strategically articulated and communicated by protest movements. Although non-violence meanings do not strictly constitute frames, but, rather, packages of meaning usually tied to frames (of justice, rights, etc.), it nonetheless makes sense to speak of the counter-framing of such packages. The conceptual apparatus devised in the academic literature to analyse framing and counter-framing dynamics actually includes certain key elements which can significantly be used for our own purposes: namely, the analysis of the terrain in which confronted packages of meaning referring to “coercive nonviolence” tactics are put forward. The most relevant of such elements is consistency, “in terms of perceived contradictions between framings and tactical actions (as between what the SMO says and what it does)” (Benford & Snow, 2000: 620). Consistency is a basic component of the credibility of a given SMO and, hence, of the potential resonance of its claims (2000: 619-620).

In advanced democracies, meanings of violence are not prone to resonate amongst the central and usually tempered layers of public opinion. Since coercive nonviolent tactics might easily be countered with meanings of radicalism, violence and criminalization by opponents holding a considerable amount of power and communicational resources, it is crucial for SMO’s central actors, when attempting to legitimize a given “coercive nonviolent” tactic, to properly interpret what kind of notion of non-violence preponderates amongst their targets, irrespective of the notions of non-violence prevailing in the academic and activist literatures. If the target is public opinion as a whole, the notion of non-violence which ought to be deciphered is the one predominating in the extant stock of meanings of a given political culture.

The academic and activist literatures on nonviolent protest actually revolve around the definition of non-violence. Whether non-violence is seen as a moral issue or as a purely strategic question, the key point is the demarcation of the limits of nonviolent action, and, at this respect, two particularly sensitive elements can be identified: psychological or spiritual coercion and its personalization.

In his monumental *The politics of nonviolent action* (1973), recently summarized under the title *How nonviolent struggle works* (2013), Sharp, within his own effort of demarcation of non-violence, extensively developed the borderline concept of “nonviolent coercion”. The first thing which calls our attention in Sharp’s works is the author’s recurrent use of warlike terminology: thus, for example, when listing the keys of success of nonviolent action, Sharp recommends a “careful choice of *weapons* [our emphasis]” (2013: xx). As a matter of fact, he clearly states further on, in order to justify the interest of his work, that, whereas “[t]he principles of strategy and tactics of war have been carefully developed and studied [...], in the field of nonviolent action, no comparable development has yet occurred” (2013: 63). Sharp indeed holds a purely instrumental stance on nonviolent protest. In his view, non-violence, the same as violence, is but a technique aimed at counterbalancing the power of usually privileged opponents. The purported superiority of non-violence is predicated exclusively on the grounds of its comparative efficacy. Moral considerations, apart from the underlying utilitarian ethics, are explicitly put aside: “Nonviolent discipline [...] is not an alien emphasis introduced by moralists or pacifists” (2013: 101). On the contrary, it “is rooted in the dynamics of the techniques of nonviolent action” (101), and one of the principal mechanisms by which nonviolent tactics supposedly outperform their violent counterparts is communication, mainly, although not exclusively, directed towards public opinion: apart from eventually helping “people to face severe repression and to make the maximum impact of their objectives”, nonviolent discipline “also *contributes to respect for the movement by third parties, the population in general* [our emphasis], and even the opponents” (104).

The concept of “nonviolent coercion” lies at the heart of Sharp’s approach to nonviolent action and constitutes its clearest elaboration of its own minimalist demarcation of non-violence. According to him, nonviolent coercion is one of the four “broad processes, or mechanisms, which can bring success” to nonviolent struggle, the other three being conversion, accommodation, and disintegration (121); the latter, nonetheless, “results from the more severe application of the same forces that produce nonviolent coercion” (126). His concept of nonviolent coercion is built on the notion that “[c]oercion is not limited to the effects of threats or use of physical violence” (125), in accordance with his previous definition of “nonviolent action”: “a generic term covering dozens of specific methods of protest, noncooperation and intervention, in all

of which the resisters conduct the conflict by doing –or refusing to do– certain things *without using physical violence*” [our emphasis] (18).

Minimalist definitions of non-violence as the sheer absence of the threat or use of physical violence, such as Sharp’s, have been the object of a long-standing debate within the field of non-violence studies. In his compelling analysis of *Non-violence in the civil rights movement in the United States*, Samad (2008) resumes the discussion from a more nuanced standpoint which, nonetheless, heavily relies on Sharp’s notion of “nonviolent coercion”. Samad analytically distinguishes the “practical” and the “moral” approaches to non-violence. As we move from the first to the second ones, the absence of the threat or use of physical violence is supplemented with other requisites, such as, notably, those related to the absence of psychological violence and the absence of personalization, as in the non-violence philosophy of Martin Luther King: “[N]on-violence does not seek to humiliate the opponent [...]. A protester fights against the sources of evil and not against humans [...] [and] must not only avoid physical violence but also violence of the spirit” (2008: 20). When confronted with the urgencies of success and with the influential notion that “absolute pacifism”, which rejects coercion, might be “futile and self-defeating”, Luther King apparently moved towards “prudential pacifism”, which regards coercion as justified (53). Altogether, “[n]on-violence during the civil rights movement was particularly successful since nonviolent protesters converted American public opinion or, in other words, caused American public opinion to sympathize with African-American demands for integration through nonviolent rhetoric and nonviolent dramatization of protest” (103). In his own nonviolent campaigns, Gandhi had as well “contended that in order to affect the heart, one had to awaken public opinion (109).

As we have signaled above, the battle of public opinion, irrespective from academic or activist conceptual distinctions, critically depends on how consistent nonviolent rhetoric and dramatization *are perceived to be*. And we have good reasons to believe that the contemporary Spanish public opinion tends to embrace a rather strict notion of non-violence, perhaps closer to absolute than to prudential pacifism. As we have mentioned elsewhere (Nos Aldás, Seguí-Cosme and Iranzo, 2014), the refusal of passed violence was a cornerstone of the political narrations aimed at legitimatizing the Spanish transition to democracy, and, in spite of the present-day crisis of the so-called “regime of 1978”, non-violence remains a key component of the Spanish political culture. The fact that Spanish politics have since the transition exhibited a

comparatively very high degree of protest has widely been acknowledged (Benedicto, 2006: 122; Fishman, 2012: 355). But little attention has been paid to the fact that much of such protest has not only been essentially nonviolent, but has as well been centered on antimilitaristic or pacifist claims, such as those put forward by the Conscientious Objectors Movement (MOC) during the transition, the anti-NATO movement in the 1980s, the movement for peace in the Basque Country since the 1980s, or the No to War [in Irak] movement in the 2000s.

The most recent cycle of protest in Spain starting on 15 May, 2011, widely known as 15-M or Spanish *indignados* (the outraged) movement, has retained the public compromise with non-violence as a quasi-sacred sign of identity, as several authors, such as Postill (2013), and Fernández González and Molina Allende (2014) have emphasized. The PAH, highly entangled with the 15-M, had generally privileged institutional tactics, until it launched, in February, 2013, his campaign of individualized *escraches* against governmental opponents. *Escraches* are a specific tactic of nonviolent coercion with fit into two of the categories listed by Sharp, under the rubric “pressures on individuals”: “‘haunting’ officials” and “‘taunting officials” (2013: 27).

2. The successful governmental counter-framing of the PAH’s “nonviolent coercitive” *escraches* in 2013

The counter-framing process which constitutes our case study was ignited by the *escraches* campaign launched by the PAH in order to achieve the support of the ruling center-right People’s party (PP) members of parliament (MP) to its proposal of mortgage law reform. This proposal included demands such as a social rent and a halt to evictions. The *escrache* is a coercitive nonviolent direct action in which the PAH activists doorstepped the PP politicians in their homes to pressure them to pass the above mentioned law reform. The analysis of that counter-framing process will focus on the non-violence meanings of the protest and will be based on the claims made by the PAH, available at its website (www.afectadosporlahipoteca.com), and on news pieces published on the online version of *El País* (www.elpais.com), one of the leading newspapers in Spain. The choice of *El País* has an additional advantage: as a center-left media outlet, it is supposed to be more predisposed to support the PAH’s demands. This fact confers more credibility to its possible counter-framing of the PAH protests as violent, in the sense that it might be attributable to the long-lasting narrative of non-

violence preexisting in Spain, rather than to the Spanish partisan press model (Hallin and Mancini, 2004). The search of the news items has been made using two key words: “PAH” and “*escrache*”.

The PAH launched the *escraches* campaign in February, 2013. The first phase of the campaign (an open letter sent to MPs)¹ was practically unnoticed for media outlets. Only when the second phase arrived and the *escraches* started (March, 2013), the news media began to report about them. The organization was well aware of the risks associated to this initiative, as shown by the fact that the press release about it highlighted in bold letters that it was to be “a nonviolent campaign”.² But this was a matter of worries not only for the PAH, but also for the papers. Short before the first *escrache* took place, a news piece from *El País*³ underlined in its first sentence that the PAH’s activists were going to follow MP’s steps in a “nonviolent” and “peaceful” way in order to persuade them to support its mortgage law reform. “Violence” was, then, on the focus of attention. In fact, the *escraches* were previously studied by the PAH’s juridical committee⁴ to make sure that these actions were completely legal. The organization backed the second phase of the campaign with the release of a video titled “From Victim to MP”,⁵ in which mortgages victims directly addressed politicians to demand their support to pass the law reform. Here, violence was, again, the center of attention: on the one hand, the video was an explicit denounce of the structural violence (Galtung, 1969) suffered by those people that risked to lose their home; on the other, the victims announced that they were going to approach the MP’s in a “nonviolent” way.

The first relevant *escrache* took place on 20 March, 2013. This direct action was addressed to the People’s party MP Esteban González Pons.⁶ Even though the PAH affirmed that it was a “peaceful” protest, González Pons accused the activists of knocking the door of his home for more than 45 minutes and made an analogy with the “coercions” in the Basque Country, an implicit reference to the violence of the terrorist group ETA. The following day, the MP reported the incident to the police.⁷ From that point on, a counter-framing process initiated by the People’s party was evident: the

¹ <http://afectadosporlahipoteca.com/2013/02/28/fase-1-de-la-campana-hay-vidas-en-juego-carta-abierta-a-los-diputados/>

² <http://afectadosporlahipoteca.com/2013/02/04/final-ilp-campanya-escraches/>

³ http://politica.elpais.com/politica/2013/03/06/actualidad/1362573953_224441.html

⁴ http://ccaa.elpais.com/ccaa/2013/02/14/catalunya/1360845209_496749.html

⁵ <http://afectadosporlahipoteca.com/2013/03/12/de-afectado-a-diputado/>

⁶ http://ccaa.elpais.com/ccaa/2013/03/20/valencia/1363797881_950762.html

⁷ http://ccaa.elpais.com/ccaa/2013/03/21/valencia/1363883737_858523.html

party opposed the meanings of “non-violence” used by the PAH with meanings of “violence”. This tactic allowed the PP to undermine the anti-eviction organization: if it was violent, there was nothing to say about its proposals. In order to get their aim accomplished, the PP politicians attacked two of the factors that sustain the credibility of any framing or package tied to a given frame: consistency and credibility of the frame articulators (Benford and Snow, 2000). The second factor had nonetheless much less impact, due to the high level of credibility of the PAH’s spokesperson, Ada Colau.

So, the People’s party mainly based its counter-framing tactic on the discredit of the consistency of the PAH’s package of non-violence meanings: “They say they are not violent, but they are”. However, it was not an easy task because physical violence didn’t appear during the *escraches*. To overcome this problem, the PP depicted these direct actions mostly as violent not in an explicit, but in an implicit way. Two were the main resources that the governmental party used to link the PAH with violence: the association with ETA and the association with Nazism. The long-lasting problem of terrorist violence in Spain since the 70’s of the last century is mainly attributable to ETA. Esteban González Pons used this fact to discredit the PAH, but he was not the only one. Some days after, Cristina Cifuentes, another top PP politician (a government delegate in Madrid), accused the PAH of supporting pro-ETA groups,⁸ a claim also defended the following day by Rafael Hernando,⁹ the PP assistant spokesperson at the Congress. Hernando also said that it is very easy to pass from the verbal lynching to the physical one. Apart from the linkage to ETA, the PP also used another extremely well known reference to tag the PAH as violent: Nazism. Antonio Basagoiti, president of the PP in the Basque Country, denounced that the *escraches* reproduced what the Nazis had done when marking Jews houses.¹⁰ Some days after, at the beginning of April, the People’s party MP Eva Durán did the same comparison.¹¹ María Dolores de Cospedal, general secretary of the party, expressed the same idea in a clearest way: the *escraches* are “pure Nazism”. Moreover, Cospedal accused the PAH activists of using violence to get their aims accomplished.¹²

The counter-framing tactic used by the People’s party had an evident effect. A poll published by *El País* showed that the public support to the *escraches* dropped from

⁸ http://politica.elpais.com/politica/2013/03/25/actualidad/1364203963_208246.html

⁹ http://politica.elpais.com/politica/2013/03/26/actualidad/1364292861_455684.html

¹⁰ http://politica.elpais.com/politica/2013/03/26/actualidad/1364292861_455684.html

¹¹ http://ccaa.elpais.com/ccaa/2013/04/05/madrid/1365164740_566932.html

¹² http://politica.elpais.com/politica/2013/04/13/actualidad/1365848717_144600.html

89 % at the beginning of the campaign¹³ (16 March, 2013) to 78 % less than a month after¹⁴ (8 April, 2013). Even though these kinds of direct actions still held a high level of approval among the citizenship, the fall of eleven percentage points can be described as relevant. The immediate PAH response to the People's party tactic was simple: to underline the fact that the *escraches* were nonviolent protests. At the beginning of April, 2013, the organization released a video addressed to the PP voters in response to the attacks they had received.¹⁵ In the video, PAH activists claimed they were not the enemy, nor violent people, nor terrorists, and asked for the PP voters' support. Some days after, the PAH spokesperson, Ada Colau, wrote an open letter to Mariano Rajoy, Spain's prime minister. In the letter, Colau rejected the association of the *escraches* with the ETA terrorism or Nazism, and insisted, again, they were "pacific actions". After the Spanish Parliament passed the mortgage law reform, with the only votes from the People's party and without taking into account the PAH demands, the anti-eviction platform stopped its *escraches* campaign.¹⁶

News media played an important role during this period. Along all the counter-framing process that took place between March and May, 2013, *El País* published two editorials¹⁷ on the *escraches*, both of them short after leading PP politicians (Esteban González Pons and Soraya Sáenz de Santamaría, Spain's deputy prime minister) were under pressure because of these direct actions. The two editorials defended the PAH's aims, but denounced the use of protests in the politicians' private sphere, and warned that the organization risked losing its credibility. The second one, far much harder, affirmed that the *escraches* were "unacceptable" and included an appeal not to use violence. Implicitly, the newspaper was linking the PAH's direct actions to violence, that is, was supporting the PP's counter-framing. It needs to be said that the *escraches* got a high impact in the media due to the fact that these actions meet the requirements to become news. That was a double-edged sword for the anti-eviction platform: the visibility on one side, and the political over-reaction, also visible in the news media, on the other. During the weeks the campaign was active, *El País* published not only two editorials and several news pieces about the protests and the political reactions, but also

¹³ http://politica.elpais.com/politica/2013/03/16/actualidad/1363470095_882443.html

¹⁴ http://politica.elpais.com/politica/2013/04/07/actualidad/1365358645_241274.html

¹⁵ <http://afectadosporlahipoteca.com/2013/04/05/la-pah-presenta-mensaje-a-los-votantes-del-pp/>

¹⁶ http://politica.elpais.com/politica/2013/04/19/actualidad/1366368353_966754.html

¹⁷ http://elpais.com/elpais/2013/03/25/opinion/1364243227_860936.html and http://elpais.com/elpais/2013/04/09/opinion/1365533241_824332.html

a great amount of op-eds. Oddly enough, the *El País* op-ed contributors overwhelmingly supported the *escraches*, despite the newspaper editorial position.

According to the police, the PAH was not a violent organization.¹⁸ Moreover, the courts backed the *escraches* legality¹⁹ when the PP politicians reported them. Despite these facts, and the majoritarian support of the citizenship, when the anti-evictions platform resumed the *escaches* one year later²⁰ to press the PP before the European elections of May, 2014, very important modifications were introduced: the protests would be silent and not addressed to particular politicians, but held in public electoral acts. The new tactic seemed to be prepared to avoid any kind of criminalization from the People's party. The outright rejection of violence that characterized the Spanish society was used by the PP politicians and defended by leading news media as *El País*. As a result, the counter-framing tactic developed by the ruling party proved to be successful. The new *escraches* didn't cause any political reaction, neither did attract the press. The PAH accomplished not to be linked to violence, but with a high cost: becoming invisible.

Conclusions

Framing and counter-framing processes play a key role in the communication of social movements. This paper has explored how a “nonviolent coercion” tactic as the *escraches* used by the PAH—a direct action in which activists doorstepped high rank PP politicians in order to get their support to its proposal of mortgage law reform—was easily counter-framed by the People's party as violent. The success of the PP's counter-framing tactic can be attributed to the fact that the Spanish public opinion has consistently maintained rather strict attitudes of non-violence across the ideological and partisan spectrum since the transition to democracy in the late 1970s, in accordance with the long-lasting hegemonic narratives concerning recent history and Basque terrorism. In this counter-framing process, the news media also played an important role. The Spanish leading newspaper *El País*, used as a source of information in our case of study, denounced the use of protests within the politicians' private sphere and, implicitly, linked the PAH's direct actions to violence.

¹⁸ http://politica.elpais.com/politica/2013/03/30/actualidad/1364669519_850037.html

¹⁹ http://politica.elpais.com/politica/2014/02/06/actualidad/1391715997_947698.html

²⁰ <http://afectadosporlahipoteca.com/2014/05/09/nueva-campana-de-la-pah/>

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